

Prevalence and Risk Factors Associated with Birth Asphyxia among Neonates Admitted in Tertiary Care Centre of Bundelkhand Region**Ranakesh Ramavathu¹, Sapna Gupta², Om Shankar Chaurasia³**¹Senior Resident, Department of Paediatrics, M.L.B. Medical College, Jhansi UP, India²Associate Professor, Department of Paediatrics, M.L.B. Medical College, Jhansi UP, India³Professor & Head, Department of Paediatrics, M.L.B. Medical College, Jhansi UP, India

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Abstract:**Background:** Globally, a significant factor in neonatal mortality is birth asphyxia. Birth asphyxia is still a serious illness that causes a high rate of morbidity and mortality in India. The purpose of the study was to evaluate the relationship between newborn outcome and birth asphyxia prevalence and risk factors.**Methods:** The cross-sectional study was carried out on 131 neonates during September 2021 to August 2022. Data were collected using a questionnaire, check list and chart review, which was used to retrieve medical information and mother's data. Data analyzed using SPSS-25 software.**Results:** It was shown that 19.3% of babies had birth asphyxia overall. Among the 181 cases of births, there were 23.04% with meconium-stained labor, 16.85 with obstructed labor, 11.77% with malpresentation, 14.12% with prolonged labor, 8.3% with anemia, 9.55% with premature delivery, 5.67% with PROM, 3.3% with preeclampsia, and 1.75% with umbilical cord prolapse. In this study, the prevalence of moderate newborn asphyxia was 59.6% and severe birth asphyxia was 40.4% overall. 26 cases (49.0%) of severe newborn asphyxia were discharged, and 27 cases (51%) died; in contrast, 61 cases (70%) of moderate birth asphyxia were discharged, and 17 cases (30%) died.**Conclusion :** Findings indicate that birth asphyxia is still prevalent and fetal mal-presentation, premature rupture of fetal membranes, meconium stained amniotic fluid, obstructed labour and prolonged labour were significantly associated maternal risk factors for birth asphyxia in neonates. Improved maternity care is required, as is raising awareness of the causes of birth asphyxia.**Keywords:** Birth Asphyxia, Prevalence, Contributing Factors.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

The incapacity of the baby to begin and maintain adequate breathing after birth is known as perinatal asphyxia, and it is typified by a noticeable impairment in gas exchange. Lack of blood flow or gas exchange to the fetus in late pregnancy, during, or after birth as a neonate is the cause of perinatal asphyxia. There is a partial (hypoxia) or total (anoxia) loss of oxygen to the critical organs when placental (before birth) or pulmonary (shortly after birth) gas exchange is reduced or stops. Hypercapnia and hypoxemia worsen as a result.

The tissues and essential organs (muscle, liver, heart, and finally the brain) will accumulate an oxygen debt if the hypoxemia is severe enough. Lactic acidosis and anaerobic glycolysis will follow. The neurologic aftereffects of perinatal hypoxia are referred to as neonatal hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy. When the umbilical cord arterial pH is less than 7, the APGAR (Appearance, Pulse, Grimace, Activity, and Respiration) score is

0-3 in the first and fifth minutes, and there are signs of hypo- or hypertonia, seizures, lethargy, coma, and multisystem organ dysfunction, the condition is diagnosed as perinatal asphyxia. In wealthy nations, the prevalence of perinatal asphyxia ranges from 2 to 30 per 1000 live births; however, in underdeveloped nations, when access to quality maternal and newborn care is inadequate, the rate is ten times higher. 15% to 20% of the asphyxiated newborns will pass away during the neonatal period, and 25% of the survivors will always have neurologic impairments [1].

Perinatal asphyxia is one of the three leading causes of under-five child mortality (11%) after preterm delivery (17%) and pneumonia (15%), according to the World Health Organization. The Apgar score, which has a range of zero to 10, is a metric used to assess the degree of birth asphyxia during the first and fifth minutes of life [2]. An Apgar score of less than seven indicates that the

newborn may have birth asphyxia. Moderate birth asphyxia is indicated by an Apgar score of four to seven, while severe asphyxia is indicated by an Apgar score of zero to three [3]. Serious asphyxia can lead to serious multiorgan damage, including necrotizing enterocolitis, lung dysfunction, cardiomyopathy, renal failure, and hepatic failure [4]. Brain damage is the most concerning of all these injuries since those who survive are likely to experience lifetime issues like intellectual ineptitude, motor impairments, and permanent seizure disorder.

Maternal anemia, oligohydramnios, low birth weight, history of stillbirth, antepartum hemorrhage, advanced maternal age, low educational status, and severe maternal hypotension or hypertensive diseases during pregnancy are among the antepartum risk factors.

Malpresentation, protracted second stage of labor, home delivery, obstructed labor, oxytocin use, and meconium-stained amniotic fluid are examples of intrapartum risk factors. Low birth weight, high birth weight, multiple gestations, tight nuchal cord, premature delivery, resuscitation, and fetal distress are among the fetal risk factors linked to birth asphyxia [5,6]. It can be challenging to distinguish between moderate and severe asphyxia in some situations, hence it is imperative to develop new methods for improved birth asphyxia diagnosis and individual short- and long-term outcome prediction.

In pediatrics, the goal of individualized prediction, focused prevention, and tailored treatments prior to the onset of chronic, lifelong diseases typically experienced by asphyxiated neonates should be given exceptional attention. [7-9].

The three primary goals of the Sustainable Development Goals of 2030 are to guarantee healthy lifestyles and promote wellbeing for all people at all ages. These goals incorporate multisystem initiatives at the national and international levels. One of these aims is to reduce the newborn mortality rate to less than 12 per 1,000 live births; to do this, it is crucial to analyze potential risk factors for birth asphyxia. Thus, the purpose of this study is to evaluate the prevalence of birth asphyxia in neonates as well as the factors that contribute to it.

Materials and Methods

This is an institutional-based cross-sectional study that was carried out at the MLB Medical College, Jhansi, during the 12-month period from September 2021 to August 2022. All neonates who met the inclusion and exclusion criteria during the study period and were admitted to the NICU ward of M.L.B. Medical College, Jhansi, U.P. were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Every baby hospitalized to MLB Medical College's Neonatal Intensive Care Unit who had birth hypoxia and a gestational age greater than 37 weeks

Exclusion Criteria

- Infants with severe congenital conditions or disorders, such as neural tube defects (NTDs) babies with fatal birth problems such as congenital infections, cyanotic congenital heart defects, hydrops, and chromosomal abnormalities.
- Documentation gaps (no measurements of the mother or fetus) are retained for review.
- Mothers who used a general analgesic during labor and delivery.
- Babies whose gestational age at birth is uncertain will not be accepted.

The information was gathered using a pre-structured data collecting format. Medical interns collected the data. Relevant data was gathered, including details on the neonate (gender, gestational age, birth weight, and APGAR score), the mother (age, domicile, place of delivery, mode of delivery, and issues during pregnancy or labor), and the parity of the mothers.

Statistical Analysis: Data was analysed by SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) version 25 and checked for normality and completeness before analysis. Frequencies, proportion, summary statistics and cross tabulation was used. Multivariable logistic regressions were performed to investigate statistically significant predictors of birth asphyxia. A p value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant using AOR with 95% CI.

Results

Table 1: Case distribution

Cases	Total no of admission	Total no of birth asphyxia admitted in NICU	%	Total no of cases selected for study	P-value
Inborn	446	62	13	46	0.0380
Outborn	982	186	18	85	

Table 2: Overall Prevalence in different neonatal risk factors

Neonatal risk factors	Total prevalence (%)
Neonatal jaundice	7.8
Neonatal sepsis	13.2
Neonatal shock	1.7
Prematurity	5.1
Low birth weight	5.0
Meconium stained liquor	5.6
Respiratory distress	40.7
Hyaline membrane disease	0.5

Table 3: Overall prevalence in maternal risk factors

Maternal risk factors	Prevalence
Primi	9.55
PROM	5.675
Obstructed labour	16.85
Prolonged labour	14.12
Anaemia	8.3
Preeclampsia	3.3
Meconium stained labour	23.04
Maternal fever	3.435
Malpresentation	11.77
Oxytocin augmentation of labour	1.75
Umbilical cord prolapse	1.75

Table 4: Distribution of cases

	Inborn	Outborn	p-value
Amniotic fluid			
Meconium stained	13	28	0.5813
Clear	33	57	
Total	46	85	
Type of delivery			
Vaginal	25	48	0.8154
Cesarean	21	37	
Total	46	85	

Table 5: Overall prevalence of birth asphyxia

Birth asphyxia	Total no. of cases	Percentage
Severe birth asphyxia	53	40.4
Moderate birth asphyxia	78	59.6
total	131	100

Overall prevalence of birth asphyxia was 19.3% in tertiary care centre of Bundelkhand region among them severe birth asphyxia was 40.4% and moderate birth asphyxia was 59.6%.

Table 6: Overall outcome

Birth asphyxia	Discharge	Death	p-value
Severe birth asphyxia	26(49%)	27(51%)	0.0005
Moderate birth asphyxia	61(70%)	17(30%)	
total	87	44	

The overall result of newborns admitted with birth asphyxia was 26 cases (49%) of severe birth asphyxia discharge, with 27 cases (51%) dying, and 61 cases (70%) of moderate birth asphyxia discharge, with 17 cases (30%) dying.

The overall result of the statistical analysis was statistically significant (p-value=0.0005). (Table 6)

Discussion

In underdeveloped nations, perinatal asphyxia, also known as birth asphyxia, continues to be a leading

cause of neonatal morbidity and mortality [10]. In addition to saving neonates' lives, effective neonatal resuscitation also helps to avoid long-term neurological consequences. In India, perinatal asphyxia accounts for 45.1% of stillbirths and 28.8% of neonatal deaths [11]. Hypoxia (lack of oxygen) or inadequate perfusion (ischemia) to the fetus's or newborn's organs are the results of perinatal asphyxia. Birth asphyxia is characterized by a combination of hypoxia, hypercarbia, and metabolic acidosis brought on by placental insufficiency during pregnancy, blockage of the umbilical arteries, or insufficient breathing following delivery [12,13].

Many high-risk factors can contribute to the newborn's asphyxia, including the mother's marital status, place of residence, employment, education, and distance from hospitals. Other factors include bleeding during pregnancy, iron-deficiency anemia referral status, gravidity, multiple births, number of ANC visits, prolonged labor, premature rupture of membranes, cord prolapse, fetal presentation, mode of delivery, place of delivery, gestational age, newborn sex, and birth weight. This medical facility serves the Bundelkhand region, which is home to numerous small villages and towns. In these areas, there are often transportation problems, delays in referring cases to hospitals, and a shortage of skilled birth attendants. As a result, many of the newborns admitted to the hospital suffer asphyxia.

The study was done on neonates who had asphyxia and were admitted to the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) of the pediatrics department of MLB Medical College in Jhansi. Both the inborn and the outborn asphyxiated newborn underwent individual studies, and a comparative analysis was carried out between them. Our NICU admitted 1428 infants in total, of which 446 were inborn and 982 were outborn. 186 babies (18.0%) were asphyxiated from outborns, while 62 babies (13.0%) were asphyxiated from inborns. The annual newborn resuscitation training programs for postgraduate, undergraduate, and other paramedic professionals are led by skilled pediatric experts. Staff members who have received training in neonatal resuscitation procedures attend every institutional delivery. In addition to being a medical facility, it offers excellent and superior obstetricians and pediatricians, committed labor room staff, and concerted attempts by all to lower the number of babies who suffocate.

In the current study group, the highest prevalence of neonatal risk factors is respiratory distress syndrome (40.7%), which is followed by birth asphyxia (19.3%), neonatal sepsis (13.2%), neonatal jaundice (7.8%), meconium-stained liquor (5.6%), underweight babies, preterm, neonatal shock, and hyaline membrane disease. In 2020,

Gebrehiwot et al. observed an almost identical prevalence of newborn asphyxia, with a rate of 18.0%. A comparably high prevalence rate of 22.1% [15] was seen in Tigray's general hospitals. Additionally, it is comparable to research conducted in other African nations such as Gusau, Nigeria (21.1%)[16] and Dar es Salaam, Tanzania (21.1%)[17].

The cause of newborn asphyxia is multiple maternal risk factors. Birth asphyxia was linked to the following risk variables in the current study: meconium-stained liquid (12.8%), obstructed labor (8.3%), malpresentation (6.13.4%), prolonged labor (6.13.4%), > anemia both (5.8%) > premature delivery (4.6%). Meconium-stained liquor (17 cases, or 20%), obstructed labor (14 cases, or 16.4%), prolonged labor (13 cases, or 15.2%), malpresentation and primi (9 cases, or 10.5), anemia (5 cases, or 5.8%), maternal fever (4 cases, or 4.7%), oxytocin-assisted labor (3 cases, or 3.3%), and umbilical cord prolapse (3 cases, or 3.3%), were identified as the main causes of birth asphyxia in our study. Numerous investigations found comparable findings [18,19].

In our study, 35 babies (41.1%) died of outborn asphyxia; of them, 22 cases were severe birth asphyxia and 13 were moderate birth asphyxia. Out of 46 inborn asphyxiated patients, 9 (19.5%) perished (5 were severe and 4 were moderate birth asphyxia).

The outcome demonstrated that the highest mortality rate occurred in outborn babies, the majority of whom had severe birth asphyxia. In a similar study conducted by Shah PS et al. in 2006, all 29 instances (19.3%) of newborn asphyxia that died belonged to the moderate and severe categories, while all the newborns who were slightly asphyxiated recovered without any problems. Because numerous systems are involved, there is a corresponding increase in mortality with the severity of HIE [21].

According to a study by Dongol S [22], the death rate for cases of newborn asphyxia was 16/102, or 15.68%. Similar findings were reported by Lodakhi GM in the India study (23). Of the HIE stage I instances, only 2 (2.60%), the stage II cases 5 (33.33%), and the stage III cases 9 (90%) all resulted in death.

Conclusion

Neonatal asphyxia continues to be a leading cause of morbidity and mortality, especially in underdeveloped nations. Many of the referral cases came from outlying hospitals, and the length of the trip could have contributed to the delay in receiving hospital care. Prolonged labor, deliveries outside of hospitals, and additional problems were caused by these circumstances. The prevention of birth

asphyxia can be achieved with appropriate prenatal care and prompt and proactive labor management.

The prevalence of birth asphyxia was 19.3% overall, and it was lower in inborn deliveries than in outborn deliveries because procedure rooms are staffed with trained paramedical personnel, obstetricians, pediatricians, and postgraduates who are trained in neonatal resuscitation techniques. Additionally, it was determined that, among all the newborns in the research, there were generally much fewer incidences of severe birth asphyxia than of moderate birth asphyxia. Nationwide training program for neonatal resuscitation so.

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